

Kuwait's Initiatives towards Sustainable Development Goals: National and International Perspectives

Atikur Rahman

Research Scholar in the Department of West Asian Studies, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh
Email: atikscholar@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

UNDP's Millennium Development Goals is replaced by its own Sustainable Development Goals Programmes at the Sustainable Development Summit on 25 September, 2015. UN Member States adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which includes a set of 17 Sustainable Development Goals to end poverty, fight inequality and injustice, and tackle climate change. The SDGs, otherwise known as the Global Goals build on the Millennium Development Goals eight antipoverty targets that the world committed to achieving by 2015. It is countless efforts by the United Nations to eradicate poverty and development of human being in inclusive way. These targets are given by United Nations to the countries of the all world. The countries have been working towards the achievement of these targets since the beginning. Every country has difference outcomes regarding the achievement of Sustainable Development goals. Still, there are challenges for achievement of these targets to the Kuwait as well as world community. Kuwait is also key state, working for the success of Sustainable Development Goals. Consequently, Kuwait has been functioning with excessive energies to succeed the Sustainable Development Goals through numerous programmes and policies. She is not only working for success of these targets for her nation but also helped to other nations to achieve these targets smoothly. Kuwait' Fund (KFAED) is key instrument to help in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals to the several other states of world. The aim of this paper is to examine what are the success and challenges regarding the Sustainable Development Goals in Kuwait and how has Kuwait been helped other countries in this regard?

Keywords: UNDP, Millennium Development Goals, KFAED, SDGs

Introduction:

United Nations has been working very actively for the welfare of human being from the beginning. UN has been choosing developmental task for the whole world through UNDP. It has been organizing, training and exchanging the knowledge among the world countries. It set targets under the various development programmes with specific purpose and time. UN's Millennium Development Goals were replaced by its own Sustainable Development Goals at the Sustainable Development Summit on 25 September, 2015. It is global agenda of sustainable development and contained 17 Goals including no poverty, zero hunger, good health and well-being, quality education, gender equality, clean water and sanitation, affordable and clean energy, decent work and economic growth, industry, innovation and infrastructure, reduced inequality and sustainable cities and communities. All countries and all stakeholders, acting in collaborative partnership, and implemented targets. The Goals and targets are stimulate action over the coming years in areas of vital significance for human being and the earth. The world countries have been adopting diverse methods to achieve these goals and produced different result in different targets. Kuwait is important country not only achieving these goals in her country but also helped other countries through providing loans and funds.

Kuwait and Sustainable Development Goals: National level Analysis:

Although, Kuwait is wealthy nation but she also has need a strategy to achieve sustainable development goals. In previous development programme (Millennium Development Goals), Kuwait had produced

excellent result towards the implementation and achievement of those targets. Now, Kuwait has shown keen interest towards the implementation of a strategy through which Sustainable Development Goals will be achieved. Recently, Dr. Khaled Al Mahdi, Kuwait's General Secretary of the Supreme Planning and Development Council stressed that his country has keenness on implementing the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), or the 2030 Agenda, adopted by the UN in September 2015. He further said that Kuwait has achieved vital parts of the UN development plan (Kuwait keen on implementing UN Sustainable Development Goals official, 2016). Hind Al-Sabeeh, Kuwait's Minister of Social Affairs and Labour and Minister of State for Planning and Development delivered a speech in 50th anniversary celebration of UNDP in New York. In this speech, she pointed out that Kuwait committed countless importance and attention for the implementation of the 17 sustainable development goals. She added that Kuwait also attached countless efforts to the achievement of gender equality, empowerment of all women and girls, ensuring water and sanitation availability, securing access to reliable energy services, promoting steady economic growth, establishment of infrastructure able to withstand, stimulating industrialization, reduction of inequality within countries, taking urgent actions to address the climate change and its effects (Arabtimesonline, 2016)

Goals: Success and Challenges:

1. **No Poverty and Zero Hunger:** The first two goals, No Poverty and Zero Hunger, Kuwait has attained reputable position. According to world hunger index, Kuwait's score of 4.9 represents a dramatic improvement in 2016. In this regards, she is biggest winner to eradicate hunger and has very low hunger rate (Klaus von Grebmer, 2016, p. 15). According to the HIES results the average per capita expenditure for the poorest Kuwaitis amounted to KD.108.4 per month, equivalent to US\$353.4 per month or about US\$11.8 per person per day. This means that the average expenditure of the Kuwaiti poor is about ten times higher than the international poverty line of US\$1.08 per person per day (Ministry of Planning, 2003).
2. **Good health and Well-Being:** Kuwait is wealthy nation and provided best health facilities to their citizens. Kuwait has reformed their health care system much more after receiving target as a sustainable goal. She has been focusing to arrange all health care facilities to the native domestically. Kuwait Ministry of Health has a plan to construct eight new hospital with the extension of old hospital. Kuwait has allotted \$102.9bn to development of health care system from 2015 to 2020. The new builds will enable Kuwait to offer more specialized treatments locally. But there are still some challenges, faced by Kuwaiti and visit foreign for their better treatment. A significant number of Kuwait's outbound medical tourists seek treatment for diseases linked to lifestyle choices, such as cancer, heart disease and diabetes. In fact, almost all of Kuwaiti cancer patients are treated abroad, as well as many nationals with diabetes (Oxford Business Group, 2016).
3. **Quality Education & Gender Equality:** These are important goals set by UNDP. Kuwait provides ample free education for all children, regardless of gender, social class or special needs. The program comprises kindergarten, primary, intermediate and secondary schooling, followed by tertiary education which is free too (Education System in Kuwait, 2016). The quality of education, be it at the primary, secondary or tertiary level, is lower than that of Kuwait's regional peers. In the Global Competitiveness Report 2014- 2015, Kuwait ranks 104th out of 144 in quality of primary education and 105th in quality of higher education (Gutersloh: Bertelsmann Stiftung., 2016, p. 20). While in Global Competitiveness Report 2015- 2016, Kuwait has 85 ranked in higher education (Schwab, 2015, p. 12). Literacy is high at 95.5% and access to education is fairly good and equal from a gender perspective. Kuwait ranks 46th out of 187 countries in the UNDP Human Development Index 2014. While girls and boys are almost equally enrolled in school, more than twice as many women are studying at Kuwaiti universities as men {(224.1 female-to-male percentage in tertiary education enrollment)} (Gutersloh: Bertelsmann Stiftung., 2016, pp. 13-20). Kuwaiti women are equal to men in professional rights and in the right to hold public position. Kuwait is improved her position tremendously and attained highest place in reducing gender gap within the Middle East and North African region. According to the World Economic Forum, Kuwait highest in closing gender gap and Index based on distributing resources equitably between men, women (Kuwait Times, 2014).

4. **Clean Water and Sanitation:** Goal 6 of the SDG calls for ensuring universal and equitable access to safe and affordable drinking water and providing adequate accessible sanitation and hygiene for all (UNDP, 2016). Kuwait has lack of rivers and lakes and depend only ground water and while has highest water consumptions in world in day. In a report published by the World Resources Institute in August 2015, Kuwait is positioned among nine of the highest ranked countries that face an 'extremely high water risk' by 2040. Previously, Kuwait has achieved MDG target of drinking water access (Carol Chouchani Cherfane, 2015, p. 22).
5. **Affordable and Clean Energy:** Kuwait economy has usually not been major consumers of energy, and their position in global energy markets over the past years has been shaped by their role as producers, exporting the majority of domestically produced oil (Rabia Ferroukhi, 2016). Heba Al-Sabah Nasser Al-Sabah, Kuwait's Political researcher state that as part of its commitment to the SDGs, Kuwait is focusing on using renewable energy including the solar energy, wind energy, geothermal energy and bio fuel finding different sources of power and reducing emissions. Using renewable energy will reduce 15 percent of Kuwait's energy needs by 2030 (Pressreader, 2016). Bader Hamad Al Essa, the Kuwait education minister stated that renewable energy is set to meet up 15% of country's electricity consumption requirements by 2030. And Kuwait has been functioning on facilitating the transfer of renewable energy techniques as well as providing applications and policies to tackle present challenges like pollution and global warming. Further, Samira Ahmad Omar, director general of Kuwait Institute of Scientific Research added that government has to a strategies to invest up to \$ 1000bn in renewable energy projects to achieve target in reality in coming next two decades (Oxford Business Group, 2016).
6. **Decent Work and Economic Growth.** The government of Kuwait uses wage policies as one of the labor market policies to achieve equality among different sectors of the economy in terms of wages, working hours, number of working days per week, and other incentives. The main aim of such policies is to encourage the youth to work in the private sector rather than waiting for work opportunities in public sector (United Nations, 2015). Kuwait holds the world's sixth biggest proven reserves of oil as such oil sector accounts for 40 percent of GDP, 90 percent of total exports and 80 percent of state revenues. In 2014, Kuwait has 3.40% of unemployment while 2.20 in 2015 (Tradingeconomics, 2017). Recently, Kuwait has launched a plan to diversify Kuwaiti economy and develop other non-oil sectors. Through this transform and Kuwait designate as business and cultural hub in near future. The plan has comprised the \$ 100 billion until the 2021 and in which \$ 15 billion will be spent in 2017 to 2018 (Thomson Reuters Zawya, 2107). Recently, Khalid Al-Ajmi, Chairman of Kuwait Society for Human Rights has launched a campaign a "Heat Kills Them" in which he mentioned "calling for law respect, workers' rights protection, the creation of decent work environment for them and provision of safer measures in the field of health and safety in accordance with international standards" (Pressreader, 2016)
7. **Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure:** Economic diversification is key issue in the Kuwait's comprehensive development strategy. In this connection, industry has a significant role to play and that develop the business which could generate the revenue. In the first quarter of 2016 organic chemicals remained the state's second-largest export earner, accounting for 2.7% of total export income, after mineral fuels and oils with 87.1%, according to the Central Statistical Bureau. The country has advantages and environment for developing manufacture sector properly. State is also more interested and encouraged to develop private investment sector that generates the employment. The country has a vision of "2030 sets of plans" and been focusing on improvement of widespread investments as well as social and economic reforms. Policy makers also want to see Kuwait as regional centre of trade and other business houses (Oxford Business Group, 2016). Recently, the biggest construction event has concluded in Kuwait from September 25 to 27, 2016. The more hundred companies have participate and presented new innovation techniques for construction sector (Kuwait Times, 2016). Therefore, Kuwait has been advancing innovative sector efficiently for the decades. In 2016, Kuwait was positioned in 67 rank while in 2015, 77 rank in global innovation index that means Kuwait has progressed in innovation sector professionally (Soumitra Dutta, 2016, p. 67).

8. **Reduced Inequality:** Although, Kuwait is constitutional emirate and mentioned equal rights in their constitution irrespective of caste, color, race and gender. Kuwait has been facing some problems to provide equality among the citizens due to several reasons like nature of society, traditions and culture of society and region. But, Kuwait has become champion to provide equal treatment to their natives as well as foreigners through passing and ratifying several laws national as well as internationally. Kuwait has granted full suffrage rights to women in 2005 and the Kuwait women comprised 47% in work place. It is highest rate of employment of women in region. Further, in 2009 election four women candidate were elected to the National Assembly. According the Kuwait daily newspaper, Kuwait Times that “the Supreme Judiciary Council issued a ruling that would allow women to serve as prosecutors and judges in 2013”(Sadliwala, 2014). Kuwait Society for Human Rights is a key organization engaging in promoting equality among the citizens in Kuwait. The organization has made worthy efforts to reduced discriminations against the women through Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against the Women. Thus, Kuwait government has made several laws to empower women in particular and promote equality among citizens in general(Kuwait Society for Human Rights, 2015).
9. **Climate Action:** Now days, Climate change is become very important issue at international level. It has posed a threat to the human identity all over the globe. So, it become very complicate and great concern to world leaders as well as academics. According to Times, Weekly News Magazine of Kuwait, “Kuwait is facing a wide range of climate change challenges including sea level rise, water scarcity, desertification and loss of diversity. The country is characterized by high temperature, high humidity and arid lands resulting in seriously degraded soil.” Further, over the next few decades, Kuwait could be potentially facing serious impacts of global warming in the form of floods, droughts, depletion of aquifers, inundation of coastal areas, frequent sandstorms. Consequently, Kuwait has actively been participated and involving in national and international level to eradicate climate impacts on environment(The Times , 2015, pp. 1-6). Kuwait, like many other countries in the 21st century face the climate change effects that are primarily attributed to environmental abuse and human activities, particularly with regard to biodiversity disruption and ecological imbalance. The year 2015 is a big milestone for sustainable development and for countries’ efforts to curb emissions. Kuwait signed a landmark agreement, the Paris Agreement on Climate Change hat primarily aims to keep a global temperature rise well below 2 degrees Celsius(Environment Public Authority Kuwait, 2017). Recently, Kuwait’s Amir Sheikh Sabah Al-Ahmad Al-Jaber Al-Sabah has participated in the 22nd Conference of the Parties to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change and stated that Kuwait has participated effectively and constantly in the negotiations aimed to limit the negative impact of this phenomenon, based upon the principles and provisions and the implementation of the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change. Further, His Highness Amir aided that Kuwait has voluntary introduced renewable energy sources and adopted a strategy to its development that contribute to limiting the emissions of greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, as well as joining in the efforts of the international community to protect the climate system for present and future generations(Kuwait Times, 2015).

Kuwait’s role in Implementation of Sustainable Development Goals in International level:

Kuwait has not only been engaging domestically but also aiding in the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals of the various countries throughout worldwide. Recently, Hind Al-Sabeeh, Kuwaiti Minister of Social Affairs and Labour and Minister of State for Planning and Development has emphasized that Kuwait has shown keen interest to achieve constant involvement towards the implementation of sustainable development goals to stretch not only at the domestic level of development, but to include constructive cooperation and stimulating the global partnership for sustainable development with the countries of the world. She highlighted in her speech the total Official Development Assistance (ODA) provided by the State of Kuwait to developing countries and least developed states, amounting 1.4 percent of its GDP in 2014. The minister also confirmed that Kuwait strategies to allocate an amount of USD 15 billion for the Kuwait Fund for Arab Economic Development

(KFAED) to support development projects of developing states to achieve the goals of sustainable development over the next 15 years (Arabtimesonline, 2016).

Kuwait Fund for Arab Economic Development is key institution of Kuwait and providing grants, loans to the countries of world. It has been involving in the development activities all over the world since the establishment. Kuwait's fund has been covering most of areas of development before the announcement of UNDP's Sustainable Development Goals to world. It has been contributing the development of transportation, agriculture, energy, development of banks, water and sewerage, industry, education and health (Kuwait Fund, 2015). Kuwait's Fund has been providing loans and grants of 19709 million of US dollar to the development basic infrastructure, (agriculture, transportation, water and sewage) health facility, education, energy, and industry to the 106 countries of the world. Kuwait has provided largest part to the transportation 33.7%, energy 25.6%, water and sewage 12%, agriculture 11.6 % and industry 6.8% of total of loans and grants (Kuwait Fund, 2015). Kuwait has done remarkable work on progress for the humanity. The state of Kuwait is always ready to help the needy people by herself, or United Nations and various international organizations under the leadership of H.H Amir of the country. The world community including UN secretary, Baan Ki Moon have appreciated the Kuwait on peace, and development activities and done throughout the world. Further, secretary aided that Kuwait leadership has saved thousands of lives especially in Syrian crisis. Consequently, the United Nation has declared Kuwait' Amir as "Humanitarian Leader" in 2014 (United Nations, 2014).

Kuwait has also provided technical assistance to needy countries for the basic development. Through fund, country has contributed 61 million of Kuwaiti Dinar (KD) for the construction of southern provinces of Gaza Strip in 2015-2016 financial year. This contribution has helped to develop basic infrastructure of the southern Gaza. In addition, 30 million KD also allotted to respond the Syrian crisis in same financial year. In fiscal 2015-16, the Kuwait has provided most of loans and funds to the health, energy and agriculture sectors whereas health sector is dominated in financial assistance (Kuwait Fund, 2016).

Conclusion:

Sustainable Development Goals is key notion which covers comprehensive development of human being and protect the future generation of human being, animal as well as environment. Kuwait is wealthy nation which played significant role at national as well as international level for implementation of sustainable development goals. At national level, Kuwait has achieved tremendous position in most of targets like in poverty, hunger, quality education, clean water & sanitation, development of renewable energy and economic growth. She has been working but simultaneously facing some problems in achieving several targets like in gender equality, good health facility and diversification of economy. At international level, Kuwait has been doing remarkable work and providing loans and funds to the developing and least developing countries. The Kuwait's Fund, Kuwait Fund for Arab Economic Development (KFAED) is key institution providing aid to nations for their developmental projects. These projects includes development of health, energy, water & sewage, agriculture, transportation and industry. She provides funds of more than 1% of its GDP for the achievement of development goals to countries. Recently, Kuwait govt. has allotted 15 billion US dollar for fund to the developing countries over the next 15 years.

References:

- Arabtimesonline. (2016, February 27). *'Kuwait is keen on achieving sustainable development goals' – Al-Sabeeh speaks at 50th anniversary of UNDP*. Retrieved January 19, 2017, from Arabtimesonline: <http://www.arabtimesonline.com/news/kuwait-is-keen-on-achieving-sustainable-development-goals-al-sabeeh-speaks-at-50th-anniversary-of-undp/>
- Carol Chouchani Cherfane, A. K. (2015). *Water and Sanitation in the Arab Region*. USA: ESCWA. Retrieved January 27, 2017, from <http://css.escwa.org.lb/SDPD/3572/Goal6.pdf>
- Education System in Kuwait*. (2016, December 28). Retrieved from Classbase.com: <http://www.classbase.com/countries/Kuwait/Education-System>
- Environment Public Authority Kuwait. (2017, February 2). *Climate change and its impact on the environment: Kuwait turns to clean energy*. Retrieved from Beatona. net:

- http://www.beatona.net/CMS/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=1812&Itemid=84&lang=en
- Gutersloh: Bertelsmann Stiftung. (2016). *Kuwait Country Reort*. Bertelsmann Stiftung, BTI. Retrieved January 26, 2017, from https://www.bti-project.org/fileadmin/files/BTI/Downloads/Reports/2016/pdf/BTI_2016_Kuwait.pdf
- Klaus von Grebmer, J. B. (2016). *2016, GLOBAL HUNGER INDEX: GETTING TO ZERO HUNGER*. Washington DC, USA: International Food Policy Research Institute. Retrieved January 25, 2017, from <http://reliefweb.int/sites/reliefweb.int/files/resources/130918.pdf>
- Kuwait Fund. (2015, August 10). *Geographical And Sectorial Distribution Of Loans Up To 02-02-2017*. Retrieved February 2, 2017, from Kuwait-fund.org: <https://www.kuwait-fund.org/en/web/kfund/table>
- Kuwait Fund. (2015, August 2). *Partners in Development*. Retrieved February 2, 2017, from Kuwait-fund.org: <https://www.kuwait-fund.org/en/web/kfund/home>
- Kuwait Fund. (2016). *Annual Reports: 2015-2016*. Kuwait: Kuwait Fund.
- Kuwait keen on implementing UN Sustainable Development Goals official. (2016, December 14). *Kuwait News Agency*. Retrieved December 12, 2016, from <http://www.kuna.net.kw/ArticleDetails.aspx?id=2581395&language=en>
- Kuwait Society for Human Rights. (2015). *REPORT ON WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN KUWAIT*. North Shuwaikh, Kuwait: Committee on the Elimination of Discrimination against Women. Retrieved January 25, 2017, from http://tbinternet.ohchr.org/Treaties/CEDAW/Shared%20Documents/KWT/INT_CEDAW_NGO_KWT_21620_E.pdf
- Kuwait Times. (2014, October 28). Kuwait highest in closing gender gap: WEF. *Kuwait Times*. Retrieved January 26, 2017, from <http://news.kuwaittimes.net/kuwait-highest-closing-gender-gap-wef-index-based-distributing-resources-equitably-men-women/>
- Kuwait Times. (2015, November 15). Amir reiterates commitment to combat climate change. *Ban calls for 'elimination' of fossil fuel subsidies*. Retrieved February 1, 2017, from <http://news.kuwaittimes.net/website/amirreiteratescommitmentcombatclimatechange/>
- Kuwait Times. (2016, September 25). Construction innovation in spotlight as 'Big 5 Kuwait 2016 Expo' opens. *Kuwait Times*. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from <http://news.kuwaittimes.net/website/construction-innovation-spotlight-big-5-kuwait-2016-expo-opens/>
- Ministry of Planning. (2003). *Kuwait: Country Report on the Millennium Development Goals: Achievements and Challenges*. Kuwait: Ministry of Planning, State of Kuwait.
- Oxford Business Group. (2016, December 26). *Developing Kuwait's export products and improving investment legislation for industry*. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from Oxfordbusinessgroup: <https://www.oxfordbusinessgroup.com/overview/driving-force-state-developing-export-products-and-has-recently-improved-legislation-investors>
- Oxford Business Group. (2016, June 26). *Kuwait moves to overhaul health care system*. Retrieved January 26, 2017, from Oxford Business Group: <http://www.oxfordbusinessgroup.com/news/kuwait-moves-overhaul-health-care-system>
- Oxford Business Group. (2016, October 25). *New solar and wind capacity will move Kuwait closer to its 2030 renewable energy generation goals*. Retrieved January 29, 2017, from Oxford Business Group: <https://www.oxfordbusinessgroup.com/analysis/winds-change-new-solar-and-wind-capacity-will-move-country-closer-its-2030-renewable-generation>
- Pressreader. (2016, October 13). *kuwait fully committed to UN's Sustainable Development Goals*. *Pressreader.com*. Retrieved January 28, 2017, from Pressreader.com: <http://www.pressreader.com/>
- Pressreader. (2016, June 28). *Kuwait Society for Human Rights launches 3rd 'Heat Kills Them'*. Retrieved February 1, 2017, from www.pressreader.com: <https://www.pressreader.com/kuwait/arab-times/20160628/281573765001550>
-

- Rabia Ferroukhi, A. K. (2016). *RENEWABLE ENERGY MARKET ANALYSIS: THE GCC REGION*. Abu Dhabi: The International Renewable Energy Agency. Retrieved January 28, 2017, from http://www.irena.org/DocumentDownloads/Publications/IRENA_Market_GCC_2016.pdf
- Sadliwala, B. K. (2014, August 14). The evolution of women's legal rights in Kuwait. *Kuwait Times*. Retrieved February 2, 2017, from <http://news.kuwaittimes.net/evolutionwomenslegalrights-kuwait/>
- Schwab, K. (2015). *The Global Competitiveness Report 2015-2016*. Davos, Switzerland: World Economic Forum. Retrieved January 26, 2017, from http://www3.weforum.org/docs/gcr/2015-2016/Global_Competitiveness_Report_2015-2016.pdf
- Soumitra Dutta, B. L.-V. (2016). *The Global Innovation Index 2016: Winning with Global Innovation*. Cornell University. Fontainebleau and Geneva: Ithaca. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from http://www.wipo.int/edocs/pubdocs/en/wipo_pub_gii_2016.pdf
- The Times . (2015, November 5). Climate Change and why COP21 is important to Kuwait. *Special Issue on COP21 PARIS 2015*. Retrieved February 2, 2017, from http://www.timeskuwait.com/upload/pdf/The_Times_-_COP_21_Supplement.pdf
- Thomson Reuters Zawya. (2017, January 31). *New Kuwait': After Saudi Arabia, now Kuwait launches its vision for 2035*. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from Thomson Reuters Zawya: https://www.zawya.com/mena/en/story/New_Kuwait_After_Saudi_Arabia_now_Kuwait_launches_its_vision_for_2035-ZAWYA20170131055644/
- Tradingeconomics. (2017, January 25). *Kuwait Unemployment Rate*. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from Tradingeconomics.com: <http://www.tradingeconomics.com/kuwait/unemployment-rate>
- UNDP. (2016, December 28). *Sustainable Development Goals*. Retrieved January 27, 2017, from UNDP in Kuwait: <http://www.kw.undp.org/content/kuwait/en/home/SustainableDevelopmentGoals/goal-6.html>
- United Nations. (2014, September 9). *Kuwait's 'Exemplary Humanitarian Leadership' Has Saved Thousands of Lives, Secretary-General Says at Ceremony Recognizing Amir of Kuwait*. Retrieved February 3, 2017, from www.un.org/press: <http://www.un.org/press/en/2014/sgsm16132.doc.htm>
- United Nations. (2015, March 1). *KUWAIT Contribution to the 2015 United Nations Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) Integration Segment*. Retrieved January 31, 2017, from The Economic and Social Council: <http://www.un.org/en/ecosoc/integration/2015/pdf/kuwait.pdf>
